

OECS Academic Recovery Programme
Report 2

The OECS Academic Recovery Programme: Synthesis of Qualitative Data and High-level Overview

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2021-02-22

<https://opendeved.net>

Commissioned by

Organisation of
Eastern Caribbean States

Recommended citation:

Haßler, B., Blower, T., Megha-Bongnkar, G., & Regis, C. (2021). *The OECS Academic Recovery Programme: Synthesis of Qualitative Data and High-level Overview* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 2). Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4780099>. Available at <https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/XAMQ949U>. Commissioned by the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States, Castries, Saint Lucia.

Version 1 | January 2021

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ARP	Academic Recovery Programme
BERA	British Educational Research Association
COVID-19	Novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2
CPEA	Caribbean Primary Exit Assessment
CSEC	Caribbean Secondary Education Certificate
CXC	Caribbean Examination Council
EGRA	Early Grade Reading Assessment
EdTech	Educational Technology
ELP	Early Learners Programme
ICT	information and communication technologies
MCT	Minimum Competency Test
MoE	Ministry of Education
OECS	Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States
OLPC	One Laptop Per Child
SPED	Special Education
STEM	science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
TPD	teacher professional development

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose

This second part of the Programme Preparation Report provides the results and analysis of the interviews carried out and a high-level overview of the initial proposal.

The evidence collection process revealed very limited literature on the four focus countries (Dominica, Grenada, Saint Lucia, and Saint Vincent and the Grenadines), which did not provide a clear picture of the ongoing situation. Consequently, interviews were carried out with some education stakeholders at the regional and local levels in each focus country. This offered additional data to address the research questions (outlined in Section 2.1 of the previous report), inform the design of the Academic Recovery Programme (ARP), and provide a better understanding of the local contexts. With these goals in mind, the following activities were undertaken:

- Region-level interviews with OECS officials;
- Country-level interview with education ministry officials;
- Strategy and consultation sessions at the regional and national levels;
- Tentative co-working and collaboration plans were established.

2. Methodology

Meetings were organised in the four focus member states, with the major stakeholders in each respective country and facilitated via Google Meet and Zoom. The meetings were recorded with the permission of the participants and notes were taken during and following each meeting. The findings of these focus groups were used both to validate or contest the findings of the literature review and to inform the development of the ARP. For full details of the methodology, see [↑Haßler, et al. \(2021\)](#).

This report is therefore divided into two key parts:

- Sections 3 and 4 present the findings of the interviews and focus groups;
- Section 5 provides a high-level overview of the implementation of the Academic Recovery Programme, based on the findings of Section 3 and [↑Haßler, et al. \(2021\)](#).

The usual protocols required for interviews and focus groups were followed [↑BERA \(2018\)](#). These included seeking informed consent, explaining to participants the aim of the interviews and how the data collected was processed and used. The Principles for Digital Development in Education ([↑Haßler, 2020](#)) were consulted to offer a technology perspective. The table in Figure 1 below provides a list of the questions asked to participants.

Note that we had initially intended to undertake both interviews and focus groups; however, because of the necessity to start the programme rapidly, we were only able to undertake a limited number of interviews and mainly conducted focus groups (see Figure 8 in Annex).

Figure 1. Questions for the interviews and focus groups

Current state of education following the COVID-19 pandemic	
	<p>What is the current school reopening situation?</p> <p>What measures/cautions are currently in place?</p>
Knowledge of ARPs in the region	
	<p>Can you name existing academic recovery programmes that you are aware of in and around OECS states? <i>If so, which populations did they target and what did they cover?</i></p> <p>What are the key considerations that need to inform the new recovery programme?</p>
Internet connectivity and coverage	
	<p>Do all schools have internet connectivity?</p> <p>Do all students have access to the internet at home?</p>
Device availability and usage	
	<p>Do all students have devices (i.e. computers or tablets)?</p> <p>What efforts are being made by the Ministry to ensure access to devices for students?</p> <p>What kind of activities do you want students to do with tablets?</p>
Regional imbalances and demography	
	<p>Are there any hindrances in access to school and participation?</p> <p>Is there a difference in demography across the country?</p>
Learning and completion challenges	
	<p>Why are boys dropping out of school?</p> <p>Are there specific subjects where there are challenges?</p>
Geospatial data	

	Do you have geolocations for all the schools with data on the number of pupils/teachers and the exact location of the schools? ¹
Social services	
	Is there a triaging process for social services? How do you identify students in need of social assistance?
Local languages	
	Besides English, what other languages are spoken? Are these languages spoken in schools? Are students taught in these languages? Do these languages have an impact on students' performance?
Special education (SPED)	
	How was the continuity of education for disabled students ensured during the pandemic?
Teacher professional development (TPD)	
	What is the current state of TPD in your country? How long is the teacher education programme? How have teachers reacted to the transition to online/blended learning? How often does TPD take place? <i>How many sessions yearly?</i>
Early Learners Programme (ELP)	
	Which grades are involved in this programme? How successful has the programme been so far?
Further collaboration	
	Do you know any individual you might want to nominate to be part of the ARP working group? How often are you available to meet up for co-working sessions?

¹ This question is important for the production of geospatial regressions. Such regressions indicate whether there are systematic influences on learning outcomes by student location.

What platforms do you prefer to use for meetings?

3. Focus groups and interviews

This section starts with a number of general findings, usually organised by country. The final section summarises challenges that emerged from the analysis.

3.1. Reopening of schools

All the participating countries reported that schooling at primary and secondary level continues, but with varying levels of face-to-face instruction.

In **Saint Lucia**, schools were shut down in March, later reopened in September, but were then shut down again. Students therefore only had a few weeks of face-to-face schooling in September and October. However, interview participants were looking forward to reopening schools again on the 4th of January for teachers, and the 11th for students. It was also reported that about 1,000 disadvantaged students at primary and secondary school levels were not reached by online education efforts during the first and second lockdown period.

In **Dominica**, schools have been closed for two terms and students have been engaged online. Schools reopened in September, but three schools — two primary schools and one secondary — were shut down for one week in November due to a COVID-19 positive case. These schools returned in a shift pattern, and for the remaining schools a smooth transition and school reopening began in January 2021.

Following the pandemic, **Grenada** opted for a blended learning strategy coupled with a staggered school attendance schedule, where students came to school for two to three days per week, with some grades coming only once per week. Priority was given to students in exit grades. School attendance is currently back to normal, with the exception of about 13 schools.

In **Saint Vincent and the Grenadines**, schools have been ongoing as usual as they have been able to contain the COVID-19 situation, with very few cases reported. They are therefore the only state among the four focus countries who still have maintained face-to-face instruction. However, participants here also reported that they were least prepared for online education and distance learning.

3.2. Academic Recovery Programmes in the region

Several ARPs were mentioned in the region, notably:

- The Early Learners Programme (ELP), a K-3 literacy programme implemented across the OECS;

- The Enhanced Learning Program which was an intervention — in languages, arts, and Mathematics — delivered through community professionals to Grenadian students who had difficulties transitioning to secondary school
- [Hands Across the Sea](https://www.handsacrossthesea.net/)² which focuses on literacy in Antigua, St. Kitts and Nevis, Dominica, St. Lucia, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, and Grenada;
- An ARP was implemented following Hurricane Maria in Dominica, which targeted all students, involving an extension to the school year. A weekly TPD schedule was introduced in schools across the country, and has remained in place as a fortnightly training. This helped teachers maintain quality of practice, and supported new teachers who joined to fill the vacancies left after the hurricane.
- Spice Readers — Grade 1 literacy intervention implemented by the Grenada Schools Incorporated; Assessed using the ERA (similar to the EGRA)
- Literacy Coordinators were assigned to secondary schools in Grenada to provide support in literacy
- 13+ Program: Two (2) year Intervention for students who were unsuccessful at the Grade 6 exit assessment.

Throughout the pandemic and previous disasters, the community and churches have remained very supportive of efforts to support COVID-resilient learning.

3.3. Internet Connectivity and Coverage

In **Dominica**, it was reported that all schools are connected to the internet via Digicel, one of the widest-reaching telecommunications networks in the region. However, a major challenge was that the internet may not be accessible across the entire school compound. as a result of low bandwidth in some parts of the school premises.

In **Grenada**, all schools have access to the internet, with limited connectivity for the entire school. For the past two years, the government has been working on a project aimed at bringing high-speed internet to all schools (CARCIP — (with Saint Vincent and the Grenadines) — A World bank funded project, which aimed at providing high speed broadband backbone network and government intranet (see annexes in Report 1).

Similarly, the MESH project is currently in its final stages and involves the provision of access points. and). Personal access for students still remains a challenge.

Saint Vincent and the Grenadines reported that internet access is being paid for schools by the Ministry of Education, but that access remains unreliable throughout the whole school.

In **Saint Lucia**, some areas have better connectivity relative to others. In some areas, such as District 8, over 90% of students do not have access to the internet at home. This

² <https://www.handsacrossthesea.net/>

issue also revealed further disparities in rural and urban communities, as more students in the city (Castries) have better access to the internet than their rural counterparts.

3.4. Access to devices

Across all four Member States, Ministries of Education have implemented device programmes, with varying levels of students accessing them:

In **Dominica**, access to devices is a work in progress. Schools are equipped with computer labs with different schools having different devices: some labs have chromebooks, some desktops, and others laptops. The Ministry of Education is currently working on the availability of more clusters of computer labs.

Some schools in **Grenada** have devices. Currently over 8,000 secondary school students are in possession of e-books, giving them access to the internet and the Microsoft Office suite. The MOE are currently working on procuring devices from different donor organisations.

In **Saint Vincent and the Grenadines** some devices have been provided to students, and the government is currently working towards procuring more devices. It was also mentioned that the Ministry's 'One Laptop Per Child' programme was never evaluated, so the impact of the programme is unknown. There are plans to transition into e-testing and they expect students to use them for research. The long-term plan is to reduce the number of textbooks and use more e-books and online resources.

In **Saint Lucia**, the Ministry of Education provided some devices but were unable to reach all students.

3.5. Imbalances within any one country

Dominica has some of the most complex and diverse terrain in the OECS with differential damage done by multiple natural disasters recently. Schools in the Western District tend to perform best in the Grade 6 National Assessment tests. However, overall, informants reported that there are no significant imbalances in terms of current access to education or inequity in educational infrastructure.

In **Grenada**, there are pockets of more affluent people located in various parishes throughout the tri-island state.

For **Saint Vincent and the Grenadines**, it was reported that students in particular on the islands of Bequia and Canouan are struggling, with some infrastructure only developed recently: for example, a secondary school was only established in Canouan in 2019.

3.6. Learning and completion challenges

Dominica reports a gap in gender performance, with boys lagging behind even prior to COVID-19. This gap is known to exist at the national level but there has been no research at the community level. One of the reasons advanced for this was that the current modes of instruction are not conducive to boys' learning and therefore not catering to their learning. In addition, boys tend to have more family responsibilities therefore they prioritise work over school. Finally, disciplinary issues and suspensions also encourage boys to drop out of school.

The situation is similar for **Grenada**, where girls consistently outperform boys in primary school exit exams (the CPEA taken in Grade 6). This is also evident at the secondary level, but to date, no extensive studies have been undertaken. In terms of enrollment, there are more boys than girls in the school system.

In **Saint Vincent and the Grenadines**, female outperformance of male students throughout the education sector presents a major challenge. This is particularly interesting as boys form a larger group in the population. High dropout rates were reported in Forms 3 and 4 (i.e., Grades 9 and 10), with the majority of the dropouts being boys. At the primary levels, girls tend to perform better than boys, and in general, female outperformance is even more pronounced in the higher grades. Pregnancy was also mentioned as a reason for dropout of female students. However, despite the stigma, girls can get aid from the social department (such as babysitting) to continue their schooling.

Saint Lucia also reported challenges in boys' performance and completion rates both in the primary and secondary cycles. Most boys fall into the lower bracket in exit exam results. Boys are disproportionately located in lower secondary schools, and are less likely to make it to higher education (Sir Arthur Lewis Community College). Even boys at St Mary's college, one of the top performing secondary schools, perform less than desired nationally.

3.7. Geolocations for schools

None of the four focus countries have geolocations for all the schools readily available within the various ministries of education; however, data may well exist in the records of other ministries. Further, geospatial data does not appear to be linked to other education data (e.g., the number of pupils, number of teachers, performance).

This question is important for the production of geospatial regressions. Such regressions indicate whether there are systematic influences on learning outcomes as a function of student location. Such regressions would be able to determine some of the populations that are most in need of academic recovery, on the basis of systematic disadvantage. Geodata is also important beyond academic recovery, for example for ensuring

equitable access to connectivity and school planning, as well as assessment of vulnerabilities due to geohazards.

3.8. Teacher Professional Development (TPD)

In **Dominica**, teachers benefit from in-service training, and a multi-approach method is used, where school surveys are carried out to identify training needs, supervisor suggestions and assessment results data. Abbreviated Wednesdays (see Section 3.2) may also be used for school-specific training by the Ministry of Education. TPD falls under the Ministry of Education and the Association of Teachers, in coordination with the Canadian Teachers' Federation. There is no specific orientation training to decide a career in teaching. However, there is a three-day induction orientation for new teachers during the first month of the first term of the school year.

In **Saint Lucia**, over 99% of primary school teachers have received formal training in a teacher training college.

The **Saint Vincent and the Grenadines** government follows the [OECS Professional Development Model³](#), which focuses on teacher training for implementing learning standards. Teachers undertake a minimum of 24 hours of TPD yearly, and a number of online communities of practice have also been established.

In 2019, **Grenada** facilitated a two-week teacher induction course for potential teachers, targeting A-level students and candidates with a degree. Inservice teacher trainees are selected and undergo a two-year training period, sponsored by the government. TPD programmes are also organised in the summer and during the school year for teachers who enter the service without prior training. Summer TPD is based on data from exam results and needs identified through teachers' expression of interest, monitoring and supervision, and teacher performance appraisals, and these normally take place for two weeks.

3.9. Special education (SPED) strategy

Participants in all four focus countries conceded that there was no strategy which catered to children with special educational needs during the outbreak of the pandemic. Representatives from Saint Vincent and the Grenadines in particular highlighted a lack of capacity to tackle the needs of SPED students. Challenges were also reported with diagnosing and assessing special educational needs in children.

³ <https://www.oecs.org/en/our-work/knowledge/library/education/pd-model-guide>

3.10. Social Services

In **Dominica** the Ministry of Education works in collaboration with the Ministries of Health, Agriculture and Sports and the welfare division of social services to provide support to students with special educational needs. There is also a school feeding programme and transport services available for many students.

In **Saint Lucia**, social services are managed by the Ministry of equity and social justice, the Ministry of Social transformation and the Ministry of education.

In **Grenada**, the Ministry of Education works in collaboration with the Ministry of Social Services to identify children who need assistance and cater to their needs.

3.11. Local language influence

In **Saint Lucia**, all students speak English. Kwéyòl, a French-influenced language, is also spoken by some students in urban areas but is more dominant among some rural students who come into school with it as their first language. Kwéyòl is not formally integrated into the education system.

Similarly, English and Kwéyòl are spoken in **Dominica**, with Kwéyòl widely spoken in rural areas. However, there are also some differences in Kwéyòl spoken between different communities. To date, there has been no formal research as to how multilingualism affects students' performance. The government is currently working towards a language development programme, which aims to promote multilingualism in the classroom, and a Kwéyòl curriculum is currently being piloted in 16 schools across the country.

Saint Vincent and the Grenadines and **Grenada** did not report any issues in this regard. In Grenada, Caribbean English is spoken widely and is the first language.

3.12. Challenges

Based on the findings above, the following challenges have been identified across all four focus countries.

It is important to note that the education systems in these Member States were already facing these challenges prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, but that the situation has been exacerbated by the pandemic.

3.12.1. Lack of a coherent diagnostic tool for identifying struggling learners

A major challenge facing the education sectors in all focus countries was the lack of a comprehensive and coherent diagnostic tool for identifying and triaging learners who are struggling academically. The Common Entrance Examinations are not very diagnostic as they fall short of identifying students or particular groups in need of support. In the

absence of this tool, it is therefore difficult to provide personalised services for students who may be struggling.

3.12.2. Low literacy and numeracy levels

Issues of literacy and numeracy were highlighted across all four focus member states. These issues ranged from low achievement outcomes in national exams to low completion rates. In some countries (Dominica, Saint Lucia), other local languages spoken at home — such as Kwéyòl — seem to have an influence on students' learning dispositions and outcomes.

3.12.3. Lack of opportunity for parental engagement

A common finding in the interviews was that there was little room for productive parental engagement in the education of their children.

3.12.4. Insufficient teacher competencies in the use of technology

As in other parts of the world, the region was unprepared to deal with the challenges of COVID-19. Among the four focus countries, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines appeared to be the least prepared when it came to preparation for online education.

3.12.5. Limited access to internet and devices

Access to the internet and devices is relatively limited for children from disadvantaged homes. Some projects have been implemented and are currently in place to target this issue (e.g. CARCIP, MESH), particularly at the school level as well as through community centres. However, even where such facilities have internet access to the internet, the quality of the service still fluctuates within the area of the facility (WiFi) and over time (internet bandwidth).

3.12.6. Data collection and monitoring

Data collection and monitoring of learning and education outcomes is still a major challenge in the focus countries. This provides a major challenge for identifying disadvantaged students and making sure they are reached.

3.12.7. Lack of capacity to support SPED children

A glaring problem is the issue of children with special educational needs who have not been catered for during the pandemic, as only minimal provision was made to ensure the continuity of their education. It was also reported that teachers did not have sufficient training required to teach them. Another issue reported was that some parents were in denial of their children's special educational needs, leading to an absence of key support in those students' home environments. These students are therefore lagging behind the

progress of others, particularly if they were already from socioeconomically disadvantaged households.

3.12.8. Low male completion rates

As previously mentioned in the first part of this document, male completion rates are a difficulty faced by all the focus countries. The interviews further revealed that male completion rates vary with the socioeconomic status of households.

4. Summary: Member State-specific focus of the ARP and considerations for ARP design

The findings in the interviews offer a new and complementary perspective to the findings of the literature review. The proposal will therefore be built on the empirical and theoretical findings of both the interviews and the literature review.

Participants across the four focus countries gave their recommendations as to which elements the prospective ARP should focus on. While some themes remained common across the group, each Member State displayed some individual priorities which it was felt the ARP needed urgently to address.

4.1. Saint Vincent and the Grenadines

In Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, emphasis was placed on the importance of training teachers and instructors to deliver and monitor online learning platforms. It was also stressed that higher primary grades (5 and 6) and lower grades (1-3) have suffered significant learning loss. Difficulties were also highlighted in subjects linked to literacy and numeracy. Informants therefore suggested that the ARP should be focused on providing support to teachers to help them deliver online learning (an activity which could be harmonised with the GPE-funded Certification Training in Effective Pedagogy for Distributed Teaching and Learning programme). They also suggested that the ARP focuses on equipping students with life skills needed to survive the pandemic, such as health and family education. There is also a need to train instructors on SPED students in order to build a more resilient education system.

4.2. Saint Lucia

Similarly, informants in Saint Lucia reported several challenges linked with literacy and numeracy, especially in the transition grades (Grades 6 and 7). Children in the lower grades were reported to have missed out the most, particularly Grade 1 students, who have missed a majority of the school year and may be lacking in necessary literacy. The need to support teachers and students in the use of technology for education and learning was also stressed. It was equally suggested that the ELP programme — already in place across six OECS Member States, including the four focus countries — be extended to the entire primary school cycle in the long term and reinforced. There was great concern for the approximately one thousand students who have not been reached during the COVID-19 pandemic.

4.3. Grenada

Participants in Grenada suggested that the ARP be focused on mathematics and literacy, as performance in these subjects at a national level has been underwhelming. Special attention was requested for boys in upper primary grades, whose performances were unsatisfactory in the CPEA examinations, and some of whom are at risk of dropping out of school entirely. Informants also emphasised the role of parental involvement in children's learning outcomes in the context of the ARP. They suggested that the ARP focus on students in primary Grades 4 and 5, in part because they took the baseline Minimum Competency Test (MCT) which provides an extant baseline for measuring programme outcomes.

4.4. Dominica

At the secondary level, some support programmes have already been put in place by the Ministry of Education. Informants in Dominica expressed interest in designing an ARP which provided support to teachers at all levels to facilitate blended learning and content delivery. Male completion rates were also a concern and it was suggested that instructors should also be trained on new pedagogical methods to better engage boys. They stressed that decisions should be based on key data such as a curriculum-based measurement at Grades K and 1, and Grade National Assessment Levels 2, 4, and 6. This could help determine which grades are struggling the most following the onset of the pandemic.

5. Proposal for the ARP

Early focus groups focused largely on transition grades, which led to an initial ARP proposal targeting transition grades. However, with further probing in subsequent focus groups (Meeting 6, see Figure 8 in Annex), informants leaned more towards early primary grades as they were identified as the students who missed out the most and struggled the most with online learning. This proposal is therefore an amendment of the initial proposal and is subject to change depending on what further discussions may reveal.

5.1. Focus of the ARP

We propose an ARP focusing on ensuring student minimum competencies commensurate with Grades 1 to 3 in literacy, numeracy, and life skills. The programme will target students across all of primary (Grades 1 to 6) who may not have acquired such skills; in particular, this includes students identified as particularly vulnerable such as boys, SPED children, and students living in disadvantaged areas.

Focus of the ARP

- Competencies for Grades 1 to 3 available to applicable primary students
- Literacy, numeracy, life skills
- Integrative approach to teaching of literacy and numeracy
- Pedagogies to include play and talk

We also note that participants favoured an integrative approach to teaching of literacy and numeracy, where teaching of these core skills is combined, as well as integrated with life skills and other subjects.

As the focus is on competencies for Grade 1 to 3, the focus on EdTech will be less than anticipated.

Participants felt that the inclusion of techniques such as play-based learning, as well as 'talk for learning', would constitute valuable approaches that need to be strengthened across the respective education systems.

5.2. Project management approach

We will opt for an agile approach. This will enable us to implement the programme as soon as possible for iteration, learning and redesign.

Figure 2. Agile project management approach

Our process involves understanding the challenges surrounding education elaborated above, implementing an initial alpha phase of the project, refining and redesigning the programme, and launching a final programme. The design process will be participatory, taking into consideration the concerns and needs of each group in the respective countries.

5.3. Implementation Strategy

The figure below provides a brief summary of the implementation strategy.

Figure 3. Implementation strategy

5.3.1. Complement MoE existing interventions

The interviews conducted in the four member states point towards already existing interventions put in place by the respective Ministries of Education such as device programme acquisition and the Early Learners Programme (ELP). We note that use of remote learning and digital devices is particularly difficult to do in primary, particularly in the lowest grades. While some integration of technology may be possible, we need to be careful to not overestimate the impact technology-based learning can have for those age groups.

The ELP is already a fully established programme, and the relevant resources and content are already in place. Instructors have also been trained. In particular, there are existing approaches to teacher professional development within the ELP and indeed within the OECS.

Figure 4. OECS Professional Development Model (↑OECS Commission, 2019)

The ARP will therefore seek to build on the relevant aspects of those initiatives, rather than creating a separate, parallel intervention.

5.3.2. Focus on skill levels, not grade boundaries

Given that the ARP seeks to reach the most vulnerable students, the programme will initially focus on ensuring minimum level competencies to ensure smooth progress and learning in other subjects. Following the identification of younger students as particularly vulnerable to disruption, the ARP will focus on skills commensurate with Grades 1 to 3, but will allow for support to be provided to students in older grades who have not reached this level of competency. Across all states, particular attention will also be given to boys who are at risk of dropping out.

5.3.3. Start with subjects where students face the most difficulties

The programme will initially focus on subjects where students face the most difficulties. Literacy and numeracy were overwhelmingly singled out in the first round of interviews. Examination score data — for example from MCTs — will be analysed to provide baseline data for ongoing monitoring purposes. Where possible, core competencies will be used to support students' development in other subjects. Life skills education, highlighted as a subject of concern by some participants, can be combined with literacy and numeracy education.

5.3.4. Support instructors

Teachers and instructors will access professional development on how to support and

monitor the ARP. The ARP will also be aligned with the teacher training programme designed by the Accelerated Fund Project.

5.3.5. Engage parents

Parents with children in disadvantaged groups will be identified and supported, for example through guidance on technology use to support their children’s learning.

5.4. Programme features

Below are the major features of the programme. These features build upon the empirical findings of the literature, and interviews carried out with the four focus countries and OECS commission representatives .

Figure 5. Key features of the ARP

5.4.1. Diagnostic tools

Diagnostic tools will be selected from the range of tools already available in the various member states for the purpose of identifying students who need support. The tool will provide data informed analysis of learning outcomes and student needs.

5.4.2. Special education (SPED)

As already mentioned, there is a lack of capacity to cater to the needs of children with special education needs in all four focus countries. Therefore, there will be particular consideration of, and adaptations for, children with special educational needs.

5.4.3. Community engagement

Community, youth organisations and civil society will be made aware of the scheme and encouraged to use the elements of the programme to support children. It is also intended that youth organisations and members of the civil society utilise elements of

the programme to support children.

5.4.4. Parental engagement

In the context of the ARP, parental involvement entails making sure children show up to lessons, making sure children do assignments, knowing who to reach out to or what number to call for assistance. Parents will therefore be actively engaged to support their children's education, and will be given information on which support strategies to apply (in particular with technology-assisted learning).

5.4.5. Strategic partnerships

We propose strategic partnerships will be established with relevant private-sector service providers — such as internet providers — to supply data for low-income households. Principals also play a pivotal role in the management and delivery of education. They will therefore serve as overall managers who oversee the implementation of the programme.

5.4.6. Resource library

Develop an open resource library to be adapted by teachers for use both locally and throughout the region.

6. Bibliography

This bibliography is available digitally in our evidence library at

<https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/XAMQ949U>

BERA. (2018). *Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research, fourth edition*. BERA.

<https://www.bera.ac.uk/publication/ethical-guidelines-for-educational-research-2018-online>. (details)

Haßler, B. (2020q). *Principles for Digital Development in Education - amendments, tenets, questions*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4516583>. Available from

<https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/PDXPLXA5>. (details)

Haßler, B., Adam, T., Blower, T., & Megha-Bongnkar, G. (2021b). *Academic Recovery Programmes in the Eastern Caribbean — Literature Review* (OECS Academic Recovery Programme Report No. 1). Open Development & Education.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4780577>. Available from

<https://docs.opendeved.net/lib/DZA3GVBD>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. (details)

OECS Commission. (2019). *OECS PD Magazine*.

<https://camdu.edu.lc/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/OECS-PD-Magazine-NEW.pdf>. (details)

7. Annex

This annex presents some additional data from the focus groups.

Figure 6. Survey response to question: What grades should the ARP focus on?

Figure 7. What subject should the ARP focus on?

Figure 8. What subject should the ARP focus on? (Votes by state)

Figure 9. Focus groups and interviews conducted.

Meeting	Focus groups and interviews	Date
1	St. Vincent and the Grenadines (interview), ministry staff	2020-12-15
2	Grenada (focus group, 7 participants), ministry staff	2020-12-17
3	Dominica (focus group, 4 participants), ministry staff	2020-12-20
4	St. Lucia (focus group, 2 participants), ministry staff	2020-12-18
5	St. Lucia (focus group, 7 participants), ministry staff	2020-12-21
6	St Lucia, Grenada, Dominica (focus group, 9 participants), ministry staff	2021-01-12
7	St. Vincent and the Grenadines (focus group 2 participants)	2021-01-29
8	Focus group with teachers (all member states, number of participants fluctuated throughout meeting between 68 and 75)	2021-02-16